

JECTION AND TECHNICAL DRAWING

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Annotation: *This article discusses the importance of studying axonometry, teaching the types of axonometric projection, the use of exhibitions in teaching the topic of axonometric projection, technical drawing and its implementation, techniques of three-dimensional expression.*

Key words: *axonometric projection, methodology, architecture, building drawing, student, teacher, education.*

From a practical point of view, it may seem that there is no need to learn axonometric projections and technical drawings based on them: in production they are rarely used, but in architecture and construction drawing they are used more often. But there are at least two arguments in favor of the need to include this topic in the school drawing course.

Firstly, it is a great educational value of axonometric projections. First of all, it is an excellent tool for developing and training spatial imagination. The implementation of axonometric projections (even manual technical drawings) clearly depicts the spatial shape and structure of the original, as if revealing the geometric skeleton of the original, and provides a useful load for the development of spatial imagination.

Axonometric projection and technical drawing are of particular interest to students who consider themselves incapable of drawing. A technical image (axonometric) reflects in one image all the information about images located in three dimensions of space. As a result, such an image is very clear, and it is almost difficult to imagine the shape of the object from the image.

Secondly, the great educational value of vivid images. Clear images serve as a link between the real object and its rectangular projections. In this case, you can prepare a series of drawing reading exercises by comparing clear images and complex drawings.

The study and implementation of clear images (axonometric projections and technical drawings) must be accompanied by the study of the system of rectangular projections and the implementation of drawings. Because vivid imagery is the main basis for teaching students to make third projection, and with it, students can significantly perform third projection in two ways.

In the school drawing course, students learn two types of axonometric projections - curvilinear angular dimetric projections and rectangular isometric projections.

It is known that in the areas of in-depth study of engineering graphics in professional colleges, special lectures and practical classes on the topic of axonometric projections are held. In this way, the deep theoretical foundations of these imaging techniques are explored. In view of the foregoing, let us dwell on the methodology for studying the topic. Analyzing axonometric and complex diagrams in a class with students will make it easier for students to master the topic and understand the deep connections between complex and axonometric images.

To create a curved frontal dimetric projection with a model, the leading edge of the object is parallel to the projection plane, and the projected rays are directed at an acute angle to the plane. In this case, the front face is projected onto the plane in real size, and the dimensions of the side and top faces change (Fig. 67). If the edges of an object are placed in space at an angle to the plane and projected by rays perpendicular to the plane, then an isometric projection of the plane is formed (Fig.).

Similar posters can be used to explain the topic. This explains to students that axonometric projections can be made on the axis at any angle, and it will be useful to jointly analyze a poster depicting axonometric projections defined by DST.

At the same time, it is necessary to draw the attention of students to the study of which type of axonometric projection to choose, taking into account the shape of the part.

figs. Rectangular isometric shape. Methods for constructing projections of axonometric axes

On the topic of axonometric projections, it is important to teach students how to draw axes correctly and how to draw images of plane figures correctly. This is due to the fact that knowledge of the techniques for performing axonometric projections of flat geometric figures is the basis for performing axonometric projections of geometric objects, models and details. Therefore, the teacher should pay special attention to the correct

formation of these skills in students. To do this, it is recommended to perform exercises on the board and in students' workbooks, use a variety of posters (forms) that reveal the content of the topic in the lesson.

Axonometric projection of plane figures

Sample Training Poster on Manufacturing Methods

The textbook describes how to perform axonometric projections of flat figures in various planes and construct isometric projections of an oval in a horizontal plane. These materials are not enough for students to master axonometric projections, especially dimetric projections.

There can be several ways to perform axonometry of objects (including technical drawings). The most common of these methods are: axonometry, starting with a flat figure forming a shape; sequential growth of parts of the subject; Sequential cutting of subject parts and combined methods. The forms contain examples of posters explaining the methods of axonometry and intended for use by the teacher in the classroom.

figs. Construct axonometry, starting with a flat figure forming a shape

Before constructing a clear image of an object, students need to systematically develop skills in analyzing its shape.

The stages of analysis of the shape of the described object can be as follows: the shape of the object is determined (prismatic and cylindrical parts); then the characteristic features of the parts are determined, i.e., the edges, protrusions, grooves and cuts that form the shape of the object. With this in mind, the exact method of imaging is determined.

figs. Production of axonometry by serial cutting

figs. Making axonometry by growing parts

Rice. Construction of a detailed axonometry by a combined method

Depending on the position of the elements of the object (from one or two or more sides), the optimal type of axonometric projection is selected: dimetry or isometry. Then the axonometric steps for each construction method are explained.

1. "From a flat figure forming a shape" (form):

- determine the shaping side and complete the drawing;
- determine the direction of the third dimension and the dimensions of the ribs;

- Determine the thickness of the described object.

2. Sequential shift method (shape):

- generalized form of the object – creation of an empty image;
- Prismatic and cylindrical (first external, then internal) scissors.

3. Method of "growing parts" (shape):

- select and describe the largest part of the object;
- growing parts of the object (first prismatic, then cylindrical).

4. Combined method (form):

- a combination of two or more methods;
- The order of movement is determined by the shape of the described

object.

When drawing axonometric images, directing students' attention to the sequence of drawing in accordance with the shape and spatial position of the object and the nature of the work being performed is quite methodologically sound, and also helps students competently perform such images.

Based on the spatial properties of the depicted object, the sequence of execution of the image and the nature of the action are determined as follows:

1. If a polyhedral object has a constant thickness, then it is advisable to perform an axonometric projection using the "flat figure formation" method;

2. Using the method of "growing parts" it is convenient to make an image of objects, the shape of which is divided into certain components and adjacent to each other, the front parts of which do not lie in the same plane;

3. When a generalized view of an object in the form of a simple geometric figure with holes, cutouts and grooves that do not violate the contour of its projections, it is recommended to use the method of "successive cutting out of parts";

4. It is recommended to use the "combined" method when performing axonometric images of objects with grooves, notches, notches and protrusions at the same time.

Images that have the basic features of an axonometric projection or a perspective image, without the use of drawing tools, visually approximate, respecting the proportions of the object, showing the ratio of light and shadow, are called technical drawings. Technical drawings have long been widely used as a means of depicting people's creative ideas on paper. Examples of the first technical drawings that have come down to us are pencil sketches by the great artist, engineer and scientist Leonardo da Vinci (1452-1519) (fig.).

When designing new models, products and structures, engineers, designers, architects use technical drawings as a means of expressing initial, intermediate and final options for technical solutions. In addition, technical drawings are used to verify the correct reading of the complex shape

depicted in the drawing. Technical documentation is also included in export product documentation packages. They are used in product data sheets.

In the introductory part of the topic, the teacher should focus on the history and practical meaning of technical drawings like the ones above, then on the types of technical drawings (form), as well as on how to perform them (form). It is convenient to make technical drawings on checkered paper. The technical drawing of each object begins with the correct axonometric axis.

In the practice of performing technical drawings, the contour is not limited to the drawing. Several methods are used to bring out the size of the details, the clarity and content of the form. These methods are based on the ratio of light and shadow, which include hatching (dashed lines), gradation (dashed stripes) and dot hatching (fig.).

When shading, it is assumed that the light falls on the object from a height on the left. Light surfaces are not hatched, but shadow areas are hatched. The darker (shadow) the surface, the thicker the hatching should be.

Due to the fact that technical drafting skills are required in many areas, we found it necessary to provide the following additional recommendations:

In the expression of professional and human relations, ideas and projects, technical drawing skills are necessary for everyone. The main attention in mastering this type of drawing technique should be directed to the development of pencil skills. Learning how to draw with a pen or brush can be divided into optional classes.

First of all, it is necessary to work out exercises in the workbook that develop the skills of correct hand placement and visual acuity. Then draw the shapes chosen by the teacher, for example, flat shapes: a square, a right triangle (hexagon), a circle.

All drawings are done by hand on a sheet of white paper without drawing tools. The next task is to perform flat figures in axonometry (figures).

On the recommendation of the teacher, drawings of geometric objects are made in rectangular isometric or curvilinear frontal dimetric projections.

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